

**DISTANCE LEARNING AND REMOTE LABORATORY IN A
ENGINEERING EDUCATION**

Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich¹

Senior teacher, Department of Electronics and Radio Engineering, Tashkent

University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-

Khwarizmi, Uzbekistan, Tashkent¹

Nurmukhamedova Tursunoy Usmonovna²

Assistant, Department of Electronics and Radio Engineering, Tashkent

University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-

Khwarizmi, Uzbekistan, Tashkent²

ABSTRACT: The role of distance learning experiment in modern engineering education is considered. The article provides a brief analytical review of remote control systems for real experiments performed on standard educational and unique scientific installations and stands. The analysis of the main methods for providing remote access to measuring equipment and controlling the measuring process is carried out. The article describes the developed algorithmic, hardware and software of the remote control system for educational and scientific experiments.

KEYWORDS: remote experiment, distant engineering education, LabVIEW, new educational technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

The present time is characterized by the rapid emergence and development of new information technologies. One of these new and revolutionary technologies is the technology of virtual measuring instruments, which allows you to create systems for measuring, controlling and diagnosing various purposes with almost any performance and complexity. The advantage and effectiveness of virtual measuring technologies lies in the ability to programmatically, relying on the power of modern computer technology, create a variety of instruments, measuring systems and

software and hardware systems, easily rebuild them to changing requirements, reduce material costs and development time. In this case, the created measuring system can be optimally adapted to solve the tasks set, taking into account their features.[1]

The use of virtual measuring technologies in modern automated measuring systems is a stable global trend in recent years. This is evidenced by a huge number of developments, as well as many foreign and domestic publications devoted to solving problems in the field of automation of measurements, control and management of technical and technological processes.

Paper is organized as follows. Section II describes fundamental advantages of a distance learning laboratory. Section III describes the role of distance learning experiment in modern engineering education. Section IV presents experimental results showing results of structural diagrams. Finally, Section V presents conclusion.

II. RELATED WORK

Also, virtual measuring technologies make it possible to combine measuring systems with telecommunication networks, thereby providing the possibility of remote access to measuring and control equipment. Such integration makes it possible to connect a large number of different measuring and control devices remote from each other into a single system.

It is very important to promote distance technologies in laboratory workshops and in a training experiment in order to increase efficiency and reduce material costs for training in the field of engineering education.

At the same time, the following fundamental advantages of a distance learning laboratory are achieved:

- round-the-clock automatic operation;
- individualization and improvement of the quality of education;
- availability of a remote laboratory from any geographical point.

III. METHODOLOGY

The role of distance learning experiment in modern engineering education: The introduction of new information technologies is the most important factor in improving the efficiency and quality of the educational process. A special place in engineering education is occupied by laboratory and practical classes. In recent years, distance learning has been intensively developing in higher education. For a long time, the main obstacle to the use of distance learning in engineering and secondary technical specialties in technical universities and technical schools was the impossibility of conducting remote laboratory workshops based on traditional teaching technologies and obsolete instrumentation. The successful development of the technology of virtual measuring instruments and modern means of telecommunications make it possible to effectively carry out a remote experiment from almost any geographical point.

The transfer of a laboratory workshop to distance learning provides the following main advantages [3]:

1) round-the-clock automatic operation of a remote educational laboratory (without a teacher and laboratory assistant, laboratory rooms and seats for students, etc.). Achieved reduction of training space, optimization of the training schedule, savings by reducing the hours allocated for conducting classes by teachers (up to 30-40% of the payroll).

2) individualization and improvement of the quality of education. The student is forced to do laboratory work on his own, and not in a group of 3-4 people at one laboratory installation. Access to work is automatically conducted, work timing is indicated with calendar time, all student actions at the laboratory facility are recorded. The teacher has the opportunity to objectively evaluate the work of the student based on the results of monitoring. Qualitatively new opportunities for independent work of students appear. The time for completing the work is not limited to 4 academic hours, but is as much as the student actually needs.

3) public accessibility of the remote laboratory from any geographical point and at any time. The educational space of the university is expanding. Education is

not localized outside of any educational building or university. A remote laboratory workshop can be performed from branches, a hostel, or from home. It becomes possible to use remote laboratories in cooperation with other universities, as well as to accept and train a student living in any city or remote locality.

Since general technical disciplines are the basis for the vast majority of subsequent special disciplines, in many educational institutions there is an unjustified duplication of laboratory workshops with their weak technical and methodological support. Scattered fine-tuning them in each individual educational institution to the modern level and their current support require huge material costs. The creation of remote laboratories with multi-user access frees from repeated duplication of laboratory benches, from the cost of allocating laboratory premises and their maintenance. In addition, prerequisites are being created for the unification of educational and methodological support on the scale of one or even several specialties, the need to develop the same type of teaching aids for laboratory workshops based on the study of the same objects is eliminated. At the same time, due to the individualization of the performance of laboratory work by students and active participation in the conduct of experiments, an increase in the quality of the learning process is achieved.

In addition to laboratory work in general technical disciplines, a number of educational institutions carry out work using special (unique) equipment, which is characterized by complexity, high cost and low throughput (no more than 5-10 students per day). The use of such equipment in the educational process is also limited by the increased danger when performing experiments, due to the specifics of such installations.[7]

A brief analytical review of the state of distance technologies in a teaching experiment in engineering education:

Due to the current level of development of measuring, computer and telecommunication technologies and means, as well as their mutual integration, remote control of real physical objects through public telecommunication networks is a global trend. A large number of works in this area are devoted to the creation of

remote workshops in engineering general technical disciplines, which are an integral part of engineering education.

When developing software for remote experiments, much attention was paid to the organizational and methodological issues of their technology. These include: protection of access to the control of the stand, identification of the user, allocation of the necessary resources of time and computer memory with appropriate priorities, provision of the installation control mode by only one user, verification of the feasibility of the specified experimental conditions and their feasibility within the allocated session time, etc.[8]

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Technology of remote automated experiment through local and global information networks:

When creating remote control systems (RCS), as a rule, the following main tasks are solved:

- 1) automation of measurements and control at the local level;
- 2) processing of measurement information;
- 3) creation of a flexible user interface;
- 4) organizing the transmission of measurement and control information over telecommunication networks (requests for measurements and measurement results);
- 5) organization of work with databases.[9]

When performing an educational remote experiment, a student cannot be given direct access to the management of a unique installation. An approach is proposed that consists in simulating a real experiment. To this end, at the initial stage, according to the experimental procedure, a database of real measurement data is formed for various operating modes of the installation. In the process of performing laboratory experiments, a student, working in a software environment, receives from the database the results of a real experiment conducted in advance. To ensure the effectiveness of the workshop performed according to the proposed method, as well

as to create a sense of reality, it is necessary to use modern multimedia tools (playback of video recording and sound of the operating installation).

Figure.1-The structure of a remote automated educational laboratory at a technical university

The main components of the above structural diagrams are:

- remote users;
- the Internet;
- main server;
- remote laboratories;
- LAN of the university;
- computer centers and computer classes of the university.[10]

V. CONCLUSION

The current trends in the field of information and measurement technologies, which consist in the development and wide use of the technology of virtual

measuring instruments in the construction of automated measuring systems, are considered.

The creation of remote workshops based on these technologies makes it possible to modernize the outdated measuring laboratory base and improve the functionality and quality of laboratory workshops.

Another advantage of using virtual measuring technologies is the possibility of combining measuring systems with telecommunication networks, which allows providing remote access to measuring equipment through public networks and creating remote control systems for real physical experiments.

The use of these technologies in engineering education makes it possible to create distance learning laboratories for engineering specialties, provide individualization and improve the quality of education, as well as the availability of a remote laboratory from any geographical location at any time. There is a possibility of access to laboratory facilities and unique stands of leading universities and industry scientific organizations, which creates the basis for the general accessibility and democratization of higher education in civil society.

The article provides a block diagram of the basic information and control element, which is typical and can be used to build both simple and more complex measurement, control and monitoring systems.

Requirements have been put forward that should be taken into account when developing and implementing such systems in the engineering and technical educational process:

- remote access to remote laboratory resources via public telecommunication networks;
- the possibility of using several remote laboratories;
- Possibility of simultaneous work of users in time-sharing mode;
- organization and processing of a queue of requests;
- processing of user requests based on real measurements on physical objects;
- the possibility of supplementing real research objects with their virtual models.

Taking into account these requirements, the algorithmic, hardware and software of the remote control system was developed, which provides remote access and execution of real physical experiments in a multi-user time-sharing mode.

References

[1] Asimopoulos N.D., Nathanail K.I., Mpatzakis V.I. (2007) A Network based Electrical Engineering Laboratory. *International Journal on E- Learning*.

[2] Machotka J., Nedic Z., Nafalski A., Göl Ö. (2009). A Remote Laboratory for Collaborative Experiments. *Proceedings of the 2009 Annual Conference & Exposition*. Retrieved March 31, 2011 from asee.org through the links Papers and Publications and Conference Proceedings.

[3] Aliane N., Pastor R., Mariscal G. (2012). Limitations of Remote Laboratories in Control Engineering Education. *Proceedings of the International Journal of Online Engineering*. Retrieved March 5, 2012 from <http://www.online-journals.org>

[4] Pop D., Zutin D.G., Auer M.E., Henke K., Wuttke H.D. (2011). An Online Lab to Support a master Program in Remote Engineering. *Proceedings of the 41st ASEE/IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference*. Retrieved August 10, 2011 from <http://fie-conference.org/fie2011/>.

[5] Restivo M.T., Silva M.G., (2009). Portuguese Universities Sharing Remote Laboratories. *Proceedings from the International Journal of Online Engineering*, 5. Retrieved March 23, 2012 from <http://www.online-journals.org/index.php/i-joe/article/view/1090>

[6] Kirsanov A.Yu. Remote experiment based on the combination of telecommunication measuring and control systems: Diss. for the competition scientist step. cand. tech. Sciences, Kazan, 2007. - 186 p.

[7] Abdulwahed, M., & Nagy Z. K. (2011). The TriLab, a novel ICT based triple access mode laboratory education model. *Computers & Education*, 56(1), 262–274

[8] Barrios, A., Panche, S., Duque, M., Grisales, V. H., Prieto, F., Villa, J. L., et al. (2013). A multi-user remote academic laboratory system. *Computers & Education*, 62, 111–122.

[9] Anderson, T. (2005). Design-based research and its application to a call centre innovation in distance education. *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology*, 31(2). Retrieved from

[10] Feng, W., & Hannafin, M. J. (2005). Design-based research and technology-enhanced learning environments. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 53(4), 5–23